

Soil organic carbon sequestration potential of agricultural soils in Europe

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Literature review and meta-analysis on N₂O emissions related to agricultural SOC-sequestration measures

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

BAU	Business-as-usual
CH ₄	Methane
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
EF	Emission factor
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
N ₂ O	Nitrous oxide
SOC	Soil organic carbon
SOM	Soil organic matter

Executive summary

Promoting soil organic carbon (SOC) storage via agricultural management is can contribute to climate change mitigation. The EJP Soil CarboSeq project aims to estimate the feasible SOC sequestration potential considering technical and economic constraints. One relevant aspect is that management practices that increase SOC stocks may also have an impact on other GHG emissions, especially on N₂O emissions. N₂O is produced in the soil by several chemical and biological processes. The most important processes are nitrification, a biological process whereby ammonium is converted to nitrate, and denitrification, which is the biological conversion of nitrate via N₂O to N₂ under oxygen-limiting conditions. N₂O emissions are primarily controlled by the amount of mineral N in the soil along with soil temperature, moisture, pH and SOC. Besides N, denitrifiers need an easily degradable carbon source as an electron donor, thus organic C plays a role in controlling N₂O production from denitrification. These potential effect on N₂O emissions need to be assessed to evaluate the real effectiveness of SOC sequestration management actions for climate change mitigation. This study aims to assess the effects of the agricultural SOC-sequestration measures on soil N₂O emissions in order to come up with a more complete evaluation of GHG-mitigation effects.

For each of the main SOC sequestration practice that was assessed in CarboSeq we executed a separate search in Web of Science. From the articles, we selected for each carbon sequestration measure the studies that fulfilled the following criteria: reporting cumulative N₂O emissions from a reported period of days, studies that compared a control to the treatment, field measurements and in mineral soils, studies conducted in Europe or in areas with a climate similar to Europe and the study should report standard deviation (SD) or data from which the SD could be extracted. The overall effect for each practice (compared to the BAU) on N₂O fluxes is reported using the Response Ratio.

In this study we addressed eight general categories and about 15 specific soil management practices. Practices with a trade-off risk (i.e., increasing N₂O emissions while increasing SOC) were cover crops and the incorporation of green crop residues, whereas the practices with a confident synergy are biochar, land-use change towards less N intense systems (grassland or energy crops) and agroforestry. Organic amendments, mature crop residues, irrigation and reduced tillage showed tendencies to increase the N₂O emissions but not significantly different from zero.

We observed a lack of research data specifically on solid manure, land use changes and irrigation due to the relatively low number of observations, especially in European pedoclimatic conditions. The overall risk on off-setting the mitigation potential of SOC sequestration by N₂O emissions appears very low. Based on the degree of implementation of SOC sequestration measures in Europe as determined in CarboSeq the potential offset varies between 1% and 29%. Although some SOC sequestration measures might increase N₂O emissions, these risks can also be mitigated by appropriate management, for example by using applying organic amendments at the right time or selecting cover crop species with higher CN ratios.

1 Introduction

Climate change is one of the six planetary boundaries that has been crossed, thereby risking the safety of coming generations (Richardson et al. 2023). The European Green Deal has set a European “climate target plan” to reduce GHG emissions by 55% by 2030 and to achieve climate neutrality by 2050. Food systems contribute to one third of total anthropogenic GHG emissions (Crippa et al. 2021) and up to 10% of total GHG emissions come from agricultural soils (IPCC 2022). However, agriculture has also an important role to play in climate change mitigation by sequestering carbon in the soil (Lal 2004). Promoting soil organic carbon (SOC) storage via agricultural management is a negative emission technology that can mitigate climate change. Increasing soil organic carbon storage, as advocated by e.g. the “4 per 1000” initiative, could store significant amount of carbon over the next 50 to 75 years (Lal 2016).

For European agricultural soils, a comprehensive assessment is missing on how much soil organic carbon (SOC) can be sequestered with different management options. The aim of the CarboSeq project is to estimate the feasible SOC sequestration potential considering technical and economic constraints. CarboSeq is one of the projects under EJP SOIL, a European Joint Programme aimed at the enhancement of the contribution of agricultural soils to key societal challenges, such as climate change adaptation and mitigation, sustainable agricultural production, ecosystem services provision, prevention and restoration of land and soil degradation, and biodiversity maintenance.

One relevant, often overlooked, aspect is that management practices that increase SOC stocks may also have an impact on other GHG emissions, such as CH₄ and N₂O emissions (Guenet et al. 2021). These potential losses need to be assessed to evaluate the real effectiveness of SOC sequestration management actions for climate change mitigation. Lugato et al. (2018) suggested that measures to increase SOC sequestration might be offset by increased N₂O emissions, depending on the crop rotation and on the duration of the land management practices. Similarly, in a review of meta-analysis, Guenet et al. (2021) showed that climate mitigation induced by increased SOC storage is generally overestimated if the associated N₂O emissions are not considered. Therefore, in order to get a correct implementation of carbon sequestration measures, more information on the trade-offs for specific soil carbon management is needed. This study aims to assess the effects of the agricultural SOC-sequestration measures on soil N₂O emissions in order to come up with a more complete evaluation of GHG-mitigation effects.

2 SOC sequestration measures and N₂O emissions

This chapter provides a general description of how the carbon and nitrogen cycles interlink and we provide a short description of the SOC sequestration practices that are included in this study and how they might affect N₂O emissions. Not all SOC sequestration practices possible in the agricultural management context were included in this study. Improved crop rotation was excluded as this is a very diverse category with many options, which makes it difficult to define the reference situation. Grassland management was not included as CarboSeq WP4 did not find significant effects for other practices beyond land use change, due to lack of literature. Increased fertilisation may be a reasonable option in low productivity systems, but it was considered not relevant in the European context. Liming was also not included, as its effect on SOC sequestration seems to be very limited. This practice was not included in the other CarboSeq work packages either, although liming seems to be a promising option to reduce N₂O emissions (e.g. (Zhang et al. 2022)).

2.1 Effects of organic carbon on N₂O emissions

Nitrous oxide (N₂O) is produced in the soil by several chemical and biological processes (Fig. 1). The most important processes are nitrification and denitrification. Nitrification is a biological process whereby ammonium (NH₄⁺) is converted to NO₃⁻ with some intermediates such hydroxylamine (NH₂OH) and nitrite (NO₂⁻) (Coskun et al. 2017). Organisms able to perform nitrification can be ammonia- and nitrite oxidizing bacteria, archaeal and fungal nitrifiers and complete ammonia oxidizing bacteria ('commamox' bacteria) (Coskun et al. 2017). Microbial denitrification is the biological conversion of nitrate via N₂O to N₂ under oxygen-limiting conditions (Butterbach-Bahl and Dannenmann 2011). Chemo denitrification can also produce N₂O when a lot of nitrite (NO₂⁻) is available in an acid soil. Chemo denitrification uses nitrite from nitrification when nitrification is inhibited by high ammonia concentrations such as in urine patches or after using urea or processed manures (Chalk and Smith 1983, Heil et al. 2016).

Figure 1 Adapted from Kool et al. (2010), Heil et al. (2016) and Coskun et al. (2017). Dominant processes in soil that produce N_2O

N_2O emissions are primarily controlled by the amount of mineral N (NO_3^- and NH_4^+) in the soil (van der Weerden et al. 2022) along with soil temperature, moisture, pH and SOC (Butterbach-Bahl et al. 2013). Besides N, denitrifiers need an easily degradable carbon source (Butterbach-Bahl and Dannenmann 2011) as an electron donor, thus organic C plays a role in controlling N_2O production from denitrification (Butterbach-Bahl et al. 2013, Guenet et al. 2021). A recent study showed that different C pools have an effect on N_2O emissions; freshly added particulate organic matter and water extractable OC had a larger effect on N_2O than mineral associated carbon (Surey et al. 2021). It is therefore likely that strategies increasing C in the soil come along with trade-offs due to undesired effects on N_2O emissions (Guenet et al. (2021). If elevated N_2O emissions remain while the increase in C stocks level off due to reaching a new steady state in the soil, the trade-off will thereby amplify in the long term. Some model studies (Li et al. 2005, Lugato et al. 2018) have shown that this might reduce or even completely off-set the mitigation potential of SOC-sequestration.

Figure 2 Interactions between soil C and N cycles (Guenet et al. 2021)

2.2 Description of SOC sequestration measures

2.2.1 Reduced and no tillage

No-tillage and reduced tillage management is often used to increase soil quality, conserve water and reduce erosion and soil organic matter losses as opposed to conventional tillage (Six et al. 2002, Lal 2015). Recent meta-analyses however do not demonstrate a large increase in the SOC stocks, but rather a redistribution of SOC (e.g. (Haddaway et al. 2017)). The derived changes on soil structure and the possible SOC redistribution after no-tillage, may alter microbial processes and therefore modify N₂O emissions. Several meta-analysis have tested the effect of no-tillage or reduced tillage on N₂O emissions, and the results often show high variability (Zhao et al. 2016).

Four global meta-analysis papers studying the effect of tillage on N₂O fluxes were already available. Three of them showed significant increases on N₂O emissions under no-tillage from 10.4% to 19.2% Table A1 *Overall summary effects of existing meta-analyses No-Tillage (NT) /Reduced Tillage (RT) vs. Conventional Tillage (CT)*(Huang et al. 2018, Mei et al. 2018, Shakoor et al. 2021), whereas the meta-analysis from van Kessel et al. (2013) did not show a significant increase on N₂O emissions. A more in-depth analysis of these meta-analyses is provided in Annex 1.

2.2.2 Agroforestry

Agroforestry systems are defined as a combination of trees and crops or pasture grown in the same field (Cardinael et al. 2017). In sustainably managed agroforestry systems, a large amount of C is stored in the vegetation biomass, and there is a substantial flow of C returning to the soil as crop residues and tree litter. A global meta-analysis showed that a land use change from grassland or cropland to agroforestry (silvoarable, silvopastoral, agrosilvopastoral) increased SOC stocks by 9.5% and 34% respectively (De Stefano and Jacobson 2018), with a large majority of studies located in middle/south America, Africa and Asia (only 4 out of 52 from Europe).

Agroforestry systems are expected to reduce N₂O emissions due to increased soil porosity, lower soil moisture and increased nitrogen uptake by the trees and thus lower denitrification (Guenet et al. 2021). Moreover, tree rows are usually unfertilized and thus this leads to lower N₂O emissions. A meta-analysis from 2016 (Kim et al. 2016) that included all possible agroforestry systems worldwide showed a reduction in N₂O emissions of $2.7 \pm 10.6 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$.

2.2.3 Land use change

Land use and land cover change on European agricultural soils to sequester C mostly refers to the conversion of cropland to grassland as well as the conversion of cropland to energy crops (Schulp et al. 2008). There are a number of programmes worldwide that examined the change in SOC after conversion mostly from a land degradation perspective such as the “Grain for Green” programme in China (Shi and Han 2014) and the “conservation reserve programme” in the US (Gebhart et al. 1994). Global studies show a clear trend of increasing SOC stocks for conversions of cropland to grassland (Beillouin et al. 2023), however, some regional studies did not find clear changes in SOC accumulation (Gosling et al. 2017). Effects of land-use change on N₂O emissions have not been extensively studied. Depending on the land-use conversion changes in fertilisation regime or soil structure and carbon content could affect N₂O emissions.

2.2.4 Irrigation

Dry regions in Europe, such as regions in the Mediterranean area, experience already frequent and severe summer drought spells (Spinoni et al. 2018), making these areas dependent on irrigation. Due to increased crop productivity following alleviation of water shortage, irrigation usually leads to higher C-inputs into the soil (Conant et al. 2001). At the same time, higher soil moisture content increases soil microbial activity and SOC decomposition (Trost et al. 2013). This SOC decomposition rate is dependent on the frequency and intensity of the irrigation events, as rewetting of dry soils usually triggers a spike in CO₂ emissions (Sapkota et al. 2020). Therefore, it is still unclear how irrigation can affect SOC sequestration.

Likewise, irrigation affects N₂O emissions, by altering the soil moisture content, which is one of the most important controls, beside N availability, on N₂O emissions. Additionally a sudden rewetting of a dry soil can cause a flush in N₂O emissions, thereby affecting the GHG balance of the soil. This pulse of GHGs is often termed the “Birch effect” (Birch 1964, Harris et al. 2021). High N₂O emission after rewetting are associated with a large accumulation of nitrate and microbial necro-mass during drought, which is subsequently denitrified to N₂O upon rewetting (Harris et al. 2021). The interaction between frequency and intensity of both drought and rewetting challenges the accurate quantification of effects. Thus, we have a limited understanding about the effect of different irrigation strategies on the soil N₂O balance at annual basis.

2.2.5 Crop residue management

For many crops, only a part of the plant is harvested, and the remaining biomass can either be removed or left on the field. If the residues are not exported, it is possible to either incorporate them to the soil or use them as mulch, increasing the C input rate to the soil, thereby usually enhancing the SOC stocks in the long term. The crop type plays a crucial role in the final quality and quantity of the produced residues both for SOC storage and N₂O emissions (Chen et al. 2013, Hu et al. 2019). Depending on whether these residues are applied green or at a senescent state can be crucial for the changes on N₂O

emissions (Abalos et al. 2022b). Fresh biomass contains more water and generally has a higher C:N ratio. Senescent or partly senescent plant materials are usually more difficult to decompose. Therefore, incorporating fresh residues can lead to higher increases of N₂O emissions compared to senescent plant materials.

Residues can also influence the soil physical environment. They can increase soil water retention capacity, thereby enhancing soil moisture content, which in turn modulates microbial processes. Plant residues can increase soil aeration because they dry out faster than mineral soil and may influence soil porosity. Overall, residues play an important role in the aerobic-anaerobic soil environments, affecting N₂O emissions.

Meta-analyses at both global and regional levels have consistently found a positive stimulation of the N₂O emissions by the incorporation of crop residues (Chen et al. 2013, Liu et al. 2014, Han et al. 2017, Wang et al. 2018a, Xia et al. 2018, Fan et al. 2023). However, this general statement can lead to misinterpretations when the maturity of the crop is not considered (Abalos et al. 2022b).

2.2.6 Cover crops

Cover crops, often called catch crops or green manures, depending on their agronomical purpose and management, aim to cover and protect the soil in periods between main crops, that would otherwise remain bare or lie fallow. This way, cover crops reduce the losses of the nitrate after the main crop is harvested. Moreover, cover crops incorporated into the soil before sowing the following crop represent an additional organic matter input to the soil (Poeplau and Don 2015, McClelland et al. 2021, Joshi et al. 2023).

Cover crops can provide different amount of C depending on the total plant biomass which varies widely between cover crop species. Furthermore, the quality of the cover crop material depends on the stoichiometry (e.g. C:N ratio) as well as the winter hardiness, some crops senesce during periods of frost and, therefore, do not provide much (labile) carbon in spring.

Besides the reduction in nitrate leaching, cover crops reduce the availability of N for soil microbes and therefore can contribute to the mitigation of N₂O emissions in autumn. In spring, after crop termination, the N availability increases again, having effects in both plant and microbial uptake. Furthermore, not accounting the N given by incorporating cover crops as N supply for the main crop may increase the risk of N losses to the environment.

Meta-analyses have reported that cover crops often increase cumulative N₂O emissions, especially for leguminous crops (Basche et al. 2014, Muhammad et al. 2019), whereas non-legume cover crops reduce the emissions or cause non-significant emissions (Basche et al. 2014, Han et al. 2017, Muhammad et al. 2019), especially if the cover crop is incorporated (Basche et al. 2014).

2.2.7 Organic amendments

The addition of organic amendments to agricultural soils has been shown to increase SOC-stocks and content at a diverse gradient of climates (Maillard and Angers 2014, Gross et al. 2021, Gross and Glaser 2021, Bai et al. 2023). Organic amendments in agriculture are highly variable in terms of type and quality and they comprehend e.g. farmyard manure, slurry, digestate, compost or sewage sludge.

Organic amendments usually provide both N and labile C to soil, both a substrate and main source of energy for denitrifying bacteria, respectively, thereby elevating the risk of an increase in N₂O

emissions. However, using organic amendments instead of mineral N fertilizers can reduce the overall availability of nitrate and ammonium, leading to a reduction of the GHG emissions, depending on the quantity and quality of the amendment.

For compost and digestate, the risk of N₂O emissions was found to be minimal or very close to zero (Zhou et al. 2017). In the case of manure and slurry, both stimulation (Han et al. 2017, Zhou et al. 2017) and suppression (Wei et al. 2020, Fan et al. 2023) effects on the N₂O emissions have been found when compared to mineral fertilization.

2.2.8 Biochar

Biochar is a material produced during pyrolysis, a process in which biomass is exposed to a high temperature and pressure and low oxygen conditions, provoking an incomplete combustion. In this way, a large fraction of the original material results in charcoal (biochar). There are different factors in the production that can modify the characteristics of the final product, depending on the origin of the feedstock (e.g. straw, wood, manure, organic waste) and the temperature and pressure and oxygen levels during the pyrolysis process.

Biochar has been applied to the soil for its beneficial effects on several soil properties, and a positive effect on SOC storage has been usually observed. Meta-analyses, from field and laboratory studies, have consistently found a strong reduction of the soil N₂O emissions by the use of biochar (Cayuela et al. 2014, Verhoeven et al. 2017, Liu et al. 2018, Borchard et al. 2019), often attributed to its alkalinity, negative surface to attract NH₄⁺, and the physical entrapment in its porosity and surface area (Mukherjee et al. 2011). Strunecký et al. (2021) reported a general increase in the soil water retention to soils amended with biochar, what represents another factor to consider in the N₂O emissions.

2.3 Trade-off potential summary

Table 1 summarizes the effect of selected SOC sequestration strategies and three of the factors controlling the N₂O emissions: labile C and N availability, and soil moisture.

Table 1 Main mechanisms altering N₂O emissions by the selected different strategies compared to their business-as-usual scenario.

Strategies	Labile C	N availability	Soil moisture	Comments
Tillage reduction	↑	↑	↑	Upper layer
Agroforestry	↑↓?	↑↓?	↑↓?	Spatial differences
Land use change: cropland to grassland	↑	↓?	↑?	depending on specific land use transition
Irrigation	-	-	↑ (as input)	
Organic amendments	↑	↑↓	-	
Cover crops	↑	↑	?	
Crop residue retention	↑	↑	-	Senescent or fresh material?
Biochar	↑	↓	↑ (retention)	Alkalinity may also play a role

The overall effect of each strategy depends on dose and frequency, with exception of agroforestry and grassland restoration, which require a system transition once. All other practices can vary of quantity and frequency, for example, the water for irrigation, the organic amendments, the duration of the cover crop, and so on.

3 Methods and materials

3.1 Inclusion criteria and data extraction for meta-analysis

For each soil management practice we executed a separate search in *Web of Science* using the terms “greenhouse gases”, “N₂O”, “nitrous oxide” “soil”, “field” and measure specific terms (Table 2). To facilitate the screening of the literature, we imported the list of publications into an AI-assistant tool, *ASreview* for systematic review (van de Schoot et al. 2021).

Table 2 Soil organic carbon sequestration measures with their treatment and control (business as usual scenario: BAU) for the different meta-analyses.

SOC-seq. measure	Search terms WoS*	Number of articles included	BAU scenario	Implemented practice
Crop residue management	“crop residue*” OR residue* OR “stubble” OR “stover” OR “straw” OR “mulch*”	17	Crop residue removal	Crop residue incorporation
Cover crops	“cover crop*” OR “catch crop*” OR “green manure*”	7	Bare soil or fallow	Cover crops (catch crop or green manure)
Organic amendments	“slurry” OR “digestate” OR “sludge” OR “manure” OR “compost”	19	Mineral fertilization	Compost Solid manure Liquid manure (slurry) Digestate
Biochar	“biochar”	10	No biochar added	Biochar added
Tillage	“tillage”	22	Conventional tillage	No tillage Reduced tillage
Irrigation	“irrigation”	13	No irrigation	Irrigation
Agroforestry	“agroforest*”	11	Cropland (tree-free)	Agroforestry Shelterbelts Silvo-pasture
Land-use change	(“land use change” OR “conver*” OR “rever*”) AND (“grassland” OR “pasture” OR “agriculture” OR “crop” OR “arable” OR “ley”)	13	Cropland	Cropland to Grassland Cropland to Energy Crop

*Other than: “greenhouse gases”, “N₂O”, “nitrous oxide” “soil”, “field”

From the articles, we selected for each carbon sequestration measure the studies that fulfilled at least the following criteria (see **Error! Reference source not found.**):

- 1) Studies that report cumulative N₂O emissions from a reported period of days (e.g. a growing season or a year).
- 2) Studies that compare a control to the treatment (see Table 2).
- 3) Studies conducted:
 - a. in the field, and
 - b. in mineral soils (no peatlands/rice paddies/wetlands).
- 4) The number of replicates were reported.

- 5) Studies conducted in Europe or in areas with a climate similar to Europe
- 6) Studies which reported standard deviation (SD) or from which the SD could be extracted.

The databases for agroforestry, irrigation and LUC were so limited that we did not consider point 5 of the inclusion criteria.

The descriptive study parameters and other explanatory variables collected are shown in Table 3. Explanatory variables for all meta-analyses ranged from climate and soil data to management practices such as fertilisation rates.

Table 3 Information collected for the meta-analyses database. Information in italics were optional and were only used for some additional analyses for practices where sufficient data was available.

Article	N ₂ O Emissions	LTE	Soil parameters	Fertilisation
Location ID	Cumulative N ₂ O emissions (kg ha ⁻¹) in control and treatment	Experimental duration	% Sand, Silt and Clay, Soil type (USDA)	Fertilizer type
Article ID	<i>SE or SD</i> and Number of replicates	Experimental Treatments	<i>To which depth soil properties were measured (cm)</i>	<i>Fertilizer application rate (kg ha⁻¹)</i>
First Author		Country	<i>pH</i>	<i>Fertilizer placement location</i>
Journal	<i>Length and frequency of N₂O measurements</i>	Latitude/Longitude	<i>Total C and N</i>	
Publication Year	<i>Season/years of measurement</i>	<i>MAP/MAT</i>	<i>Bulk density (g cm⁻³)</i>	
		Crop	<i>SOC (g kg⁻¹), SOC stock (Mg ha⁻¹)</i>	

3.2 Data analysis

The overall effect for each practice (compared to the BAU) on N₂O fluxes is reported. The effect size was calculated using the Response Ratio (RR), which is the natural log of the average cumulative N₂O emissions at the treatment sites ($\bar{X}_{treatment}$) over the average of the control sites ($\bar{X}_{control}$):

$$\ln(RR) = \ln\left(\frac{\bar{X}_{treatment}}{\bar{X}_{control}}\right)$$

From each publication, we chose to use the cumulative N₂O emissions reported over the entire study period of that publication. Next to the response ratio, we also included the raw mean difference (RMD), which gives an indication of the absolute difference in N₂O emissions:

$$RMD = \bar{X}_{treatment} - \bar{X}_{control}$$

The “escalc” function from the “metafor” R package (Viechtbauer 2010) was used to calculate the effect size of each pair. When publications did not report the standard error or standard deviation we used the EX-TRACT tool to calculate the pooled standard deviation (Acutis et al. 2022) based on model parameters described in the publication when other statistic information was reported like stars or letters, and their respective post-hoc method. For agroforestry, land use change and irrigation, we

used the average variance from the other publications to calculate the estimated variance for the studies without standard deviation due to the very limited number of datasets.

Outliers were identified by plotting the distribution of the effect size, and were removed visually only in specific cases (when the calculated effect size surpassed three times the normal variation of the data).

The function “rma.mv” was used for the model, which stands for meta-analysis via multivariate (multilevel) linear mixed-effects models. This model can account for moderators as random effects. We used the location (LocationID) in all models as a random factor to account for differences in number of observations conducted in the same experimental station, while keeping other locations reported in the same study. Additionally, this accounts for non-independence of the data.

The influence of other parameters (such as soil pH, texture, soil organic carbon, climate variables, etc.) on the effect sizes was tested by using either meta-regression (numerical variables) or sub-group analysis (categorical variables) for practices with enough observations. The “lme” function from the “lmer” package, was used to test the relationship between continuous explanatory parameters and Ln(RR) of the effect size. The continuous variable was included as a fixed effect and “LocationID” as the random effect.

For the summary of all practices, the effect sizes were converted to % increase or decrease in N₂O emissions by:

$$\% \Delta N_2O = 100 * (e^{RR} - 1)$$

4 Results

The results of the individual meta-analyses for each SOC sequestration measure on the N₂O fluxes are provided, including the location of the selected studies in the main text of the report. In Annex 2, funnel plots are provided for the data points to show the precision and results of individual studies, where the precise studies should lay closer to the overall effect and the less precise, wider at the bottom. In Annex 3, the forest plots for the response ratio for each of the individual data points is provided, and in Annex 4, the same forest plots but for the raw mean difference approach.

4.1 Agroforestry

11 publications (42 observations) were included in the meta-analysis, with only one of them executed in Europe (Germany, two observations), the remaining 10 publications were located in North and South America. Due to the limited number of publications, all studies were selected regardless of climatic zones (Figure 3).

Agroforestry

A: Europe

B: World

Figure 3 The publications selected for the agroforestry meta-analysis shown on the map.

Overall, conversion to agroforestry reduced N₂O emissions (Figure 4, $p < 0.01$) by 54% (Table 4). For the individual conversions, only the cropland to shelterbelt and grassland to silvopasture changes led to significant reductions in N₂O fluxes, of 70% and 80%, respectively.

The “raw mean difference” showed a non-significant reduction of 0.92 kg N₂O-N ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ between the agroforestry land cover and the corresponding control.

Figure 4 Agroforestry forest plot showing the increase or decrease in N₂O emissions for each conversion in land use. The x-axis shows the ln(mean/control). A ln(R) above zero indicates an increase in N₂O emissions after conversion and a ln(R) below zero shows a decrease in emissions. When the confidence interval doesn't cross the zero line it indicates a significant difference.

Figure 5 Agroforestry forest plot showing the increase or decrease in N₂O emissions for each conversion in land use. The x-axis shows the raw mean difference. When the confidence interval doesn't cross the zero line it indicates a significant difference.

4.2 Land use change

13 publications (76 observations) were included in the meta-analysis, with only three of them executed in Europe. The remaining 10 publications were selected regardless of climatic zone (Figure 6).

Figure 6 The publications selected for the Land use change meta-analysis shown on the map.

For land use change the results largely depended on the type of land use change. Conversion of cropland to energy crop or grassland reduced N_2O emissions significantly (95%), although this is based on only a limited number of studies ($n=5$). For conversion of grassland to cropland (not a SOC sequestration measure), the N_2O emission increased significantly (105%), and this was based on a large number of studies (Figure 7, $n=56$). This implies that preventing the ploughing of grassland is an important measure to mitigate N_2O emissions. When we express the land use change effects in raw mean difference, we see that all conversions increased emissions of N_2O , yet the variation is large considering the small amount of data available (Figure 8).

Figure 7 LUC forest plot showing the increase or decrease in N₂O emissions for each conversion in land use. The x-axis shows the ln(mean/control), a ln(R) above zero indicates an increase in N₂O emissions after conversion and a ln(R) below zero shows a decrease in emissions. When the confidence interval doesn't cross the zero line it indicates a significant difference.

Figure 8 LUC forest plot showing the change in N₂O emissions for each land use change based on the raw mean difference.

4.3 Irrigation

13 publications (184 observations) were included in the meta-analysis. Very few, only three, publications were from Europe with no studies from the Mediterranean where irrigation is most common, the remaining 10 were selected worldwide regardless of climatic zone (Figure 9).

Irrigation

A: Europe

B: World

Figure 9 The publications selected for the irrigation meta-analysis shown on the map.

There was a non-significant trend towards an increase in N_2O emissions when the soil was irrigated compared to non-irrigated soils (Fig. A10; effect size of 0.16; CI[-0.03, 0.35]). Meta-regression with continuous soil and climatic parameters (soil pH, N content, Clay content and Actual precipitation or MAP) did not significantly explain any of the variation in N_2O emission response to irrigation (data not shown). The raw mean difference showed an average increase of 0.3 kg N_2O /ha when irrigation is applied compared to no irrigation.

4.4 Reduced and no tillage

22 publications (86 observations) were included in the meta-analysis, 18 of them from Europe (and four additional ones from outside Europe but in similar climatic zones (Figure 10).

Tillage

A: Europe

B: World

Figure 10 Distribution of the study sites included in the metaanalyses. Points indicate sites that measure N₂O emissions in no-tillage and reduced tillage compared to conventional tillage

Overall, no-tillage and reduced tillage did not significantly affect N₂O emissions (Figure 11; effect size of 0.12; CI[-0.08, 0.32]). The effect of no-tillage compared to conventional tillage slightly (but not significantly) increased N₂O emissions (CI: -0.05 to 0.35), the effect of reduced tillage was even lower 0.08, CI: -0.13 to 0.30).

Figure 11 The effects, expressed as response ratio, of reduced tillage and no tillage on N₂O emissions compared to conventional tillage

When looking at the raw mean difference there is a tendency for an increase in N₂O emissions when no- or reduced tillage is applied to the soil. Yet this increase is small and not significant (0.27 kg N₂O-N/ha/yr).

Figure 12 The effects, expressed as raw mean difference, of reduced tillage and no tillage on N₂O emissions compared to conventional tillage

We tested the effect on soil N₂O emissions of the experimental length, the climate (MAP and MAT), soil texture (percentage of soil and clay), soil pH, SOC, soil N, soil C:N and fertilization rate. Our results showed that the amount of soil N had a positive effect on the N₂O emission increased due to adoption of no-tillage or reduced tillage, whereas the percentage of clay modulated the N₂O emission difference between the No till and the conventional tillage system, yet not in the RT vs. CT (Figure 13). The other parameters did not significantly affect the relationship between tillage practice and N₂O emissions (data not shown).

Figure 13 Relationship between soil clay content and the effect size of A) no-tillage and B) reduced tillage on N₂O emissions compared to conventional tillage.

4.5 Crop residue management

After selection, 10 studies (69 observations) conducted in 13 sites in Europe (Figure 14) were included in the meta-analysis. Most of the studies were conducted in the United Kingdom and Germany.

Figure 14 The publications selected for the meta-analysis on crop residues in Europe.

Figure 15 The effects, expressed as response ratio, of crop residue incorporation on N₂O emissions compared to crop residue removal for three residue categories.

Overall, the incorporation of residues significantly increased the N₂O emissions (Figure 15; effect size of 0.44; CI[0.11, 0.77]), which is an increase by 55% or 0.71 kg N₂O ha⁻¹ based on the raw mean difference (Figure 16). When separating into groups, only for the green plant biomass (residues from vegetables mainly) showed significant differences, while for straw the effect is non-significant.

Figure 16 The effects, expressed as raw mean difference, of crop residue incorporation on N₂O emissions compared to crop residue removal for three residue categories.

4.6 Organic amendments (includes cover crops)

For organic amendments 26 publications with 141 observations from 28 sites were included (Figure 17).

Figure 17 The publications selected for the meta-analysis on organic amendments (green manures as cover crops, farmyard manure, compost, digestate, slurry and combinations) shown on the map.

Figure 18 The effects, expressed as response ratio, of different organic amendments on N₂O emissions compared to mineral fertilizer alone.

Figure 19 The effects, expressed as raw mean difference, of different organic amendments on N₂O emissions compared to mineral fertilizer alone.

Addition of organic amendments did not result in increased N₂O emissions. When separating the results into groups (Figure 17), the significance is only for green manure (cover crops), which increases N₂O emissions. Compost, on the other hand, remains close to the zero line. Slurry and treatments with combinations (for example, with biochar), tend to decrease the emissions but also did not significantly.

Using raw mean differences, the use of organic amendments decreases 0.016 kg N₂O/ha compared to the use of mineral fertilizers without organic amendment.

4.7 Biochar

For biochar 10 studies with 24 observations in 12 sites were included in the analysis (Figure 20).

Figure 20 The publications selected for the meta-analysis on biochar shown on the map.

Figure 21. Forestplot showing all the individual studies included in the meta-analysis for biochar.

Overall, the addition of biochar significantly decreased N₂O emissions by 61% (Figure 20; effect size of -0.39; CI[-0.68, -0.11]), or 0.7 kg N₂O ha⁻¹. Looking at the individual studies, 7 observations showed significant reductions, 16 observations showed no significant effect and only for one observation a significant increase of N₂O fluxes due to the use of biochar was detected (Figure 20).

5 Discussion

5.1 Overview of results

Our work provides one of the most comprehensive overviews on the effects of soil management practices on soil N₂O emissions (Table 4). While several meta-analyses were already available, this is, to our knowledge, the first work addressing eight general categories and about 15 specific soil management strategies. Thus, from the whole spectrum of practices, we are able to classify three main types of measures depending on their effect on soil N₂O emissions: i) those showing a clear soil N₂O mitigation effect (e.g. biochar), those ones showing a trade-off effect due to increased soil N₂O fluxes (e.g. cover crops): iii) those showing a variable/uncertain result, without clear/consistent effects on soil N₂O emissions (e.g. tillage management).

Table 4 Summary results of all meta-analysis conducted on the below mentioned carbon sequestration measures.

Carbon sequestration measure	% change in N ₂ O emissions	n	Significance ¹
Tillage:	+12%	86	n.s.
- No tillage	+16 %	45	n.s.
- Reduced tillage	+8 %	41	n.s.
Agroforestry	-54 %	41	**
Land use change:			
- Grassland to Cropland	+105 %	68	*
- Grassland to Energy Crop	-60 %	5	*
- Cropland to Grassland	-95 %	5	***
- Cropland to Energy Crop	-92 %	5	***
Irrigation	+17 %	49	n.s.
Crop residues:			
- Green plant biomass	+161%	37	**
- Mature aboveground biomass	+17%	17	n.s.
- Straw	+22%	10	n.s.
Cover crops as green manure	+52 %	38	*
Organic amendments:			
- Livestock manure	+10 %	5	n.s.
- Slurry	-17 %	50	n.s.
- Compost	+4 %	15	n.s.
- Digestate	+19 %	14	n.s.
- Combinations	+15 %	19	n.s.
Biochar	-32 %	24	**

¹ p<0.05 = *, p<0.01 = **, p<0.001 = ***, n.s. = not significant

Land use change to either grassland or to energy crop, as well as agroforestry and biochar application, are the measures that show a significant reduction in N₂O emissions. Diaz-Pines et al. (2017) observed

how N₂O emissions decrease over time, due to the strong N input reduction, i.e., the transition to a less intensive system, which can be the explanation for lower N₂O emissions for land use change to grassland or to energy crop. For agroforestry the lower fertilization around the trees, but probably also the more efficient use of nitrogen can explain the lower N₂O emissions. For biochar the mechanism is probably different, as biochar is recalcitrant C, it modulates the pH and has plenty of active surface (affecting nutrient availability), all of them resulting in an attenuation of N₂O fluxes.

Incorporation of green biomass and application of cover crops were SOC sequestration measures which showed a significant increase in N₂O emissions according to the meta-analyses. Both are practices that involve the incorporation of material with low C:N, that provide labile C and available N to denitrifiers, responsible of such increase, especially if this happens together with mineral fertilization. Cover crops might have a risk on increased N₂O emissions, but there are also options to mitigate this risk. For example, by selecting appropriate cover crop types (e.g. species with higher CN ratios (Abdalla et al. (2019))), the incorporation of the residues at the right time and the fertilizer management (reduce fertilizer input after cover crops).

For the other measures, the effects were not significant, as the effect on N₂O emissions are very variable. In the specific case of organic amendments, the neutral effect might be the N supply to the crops, since most studies compare the organic amendment against mineral fertilization in the same or similar N dose.

The conversion of grassland to cropland increases N₂O emissions. This practice is clearly not a SOC sequestration measure, but here we show that it leads also to increased N₂O fluxes, having therefore a double warming effect for our climate. Preventing the conversion of permanent grassland is an important measure for SOC loss mitigation as well as N₂O emission reduction.

5.2 Limitations

As can be seen from Table 4, the number of data points is still limited for many of the SOC sequestration measures (especially for land use change). Results are therefore quite uncertain and therefore future research is required to establish more conclusive evidence, especially in specific European environmental zones. One of the issues regarding these measures is that variability is high due to other factors, such as climate and soil properties. Therefore, measures may have contrasting effects depending on the location, or weather conditions. For example, there were no data points available in the Mediterranean region to assess irrigation effects; thus, our results on irrigation are based on results from either non-European soils or areas (Hungary, Germany, Finland) having different bio-physical conditions

In this study, only the impacts of the direct N₂O soil emissions were assessed. In addition, some the SOC sequestration practices might also impact the indirect N₂O emissions related to volatilization of ammonia emission and the leaching and runoff of nitrogen. The impact on ammonia emissions is mainly determined by changes in the management of organic amendments, e.g. replacing the application of slurry by compost will reduce ammonia emissions. SOC sequestration measures can have more impacts on nitrogen leaching and runoff. Reduced tillage and no-tillage might result in less losses of nitrogen due to runoff and erosion, incorporation of straw might immobilise nitrogen and reduce N leaching. Cover crops can also reduce leaching of nitrate during the fallow season (e.g. Thapa et al. (2018)) and biochar has also the ability to reduce N leaching (Liu et al. 2019). Overall, a reduction

of the indirect N₂O emissions is expected when introducing SOC sequestration practices. In the CarboSeq Deliverable 5.3 (Nikolaus and Lesschen 2024) the impact of SOC sequestration measures on other GHG emissions has been evaluated.

5.3 Comparison with SOC sequestration rate

To know the impact of the potential increase or decrease in N₂O emissions on the SOC sequestration potential, we made a rough comparison with the C sequestration results from the CarboSeq project. Seidel et al. (2024) determined the area of implementation of selected agricultural SOC sequestration and calculated an EU level sequestration potential. The carbon stock change factors (also sometimes called emission factors) are based on meta-analyses/reviews of European based studies as reported by Panagea et al. (2023) and Seidel et al. (2024). For land use changes and organic amendments no area of implementation and sequestration potential was estimated.

These SOC sequestration rates were compared to the changes in N₂O emissions as determined in this study. For the comparison, we aimed at transforming both C sequestration rates and N₂O emissions to CO₂-equivalents (CO₂-eq). The N₂O global warming potential value of the Sixth IPCC assessment was used, which is 273 times the warming potential of CO₂. We used two approaches for the changes in N₂O emissions, one based on the logarithmic response ratio from the meta-analysis, and one based on the raw mean difference approach. The response ratio approach is the most appropriate one to consider small and large changes, but as this only provides a relative change, the reference N₂O emissions need to be known. We estimated this reference emission based on data from the national GHG inventory. According to the EU National Inventory report, the total N₂O emissions from mineral and organic fertilizer application, urine and dung on pasture land and crop residues was 313 Gg N₂O for the year 2021. The total area of agricultural land in the EU27 is about 157 million ha, which results in an average N₂O emission of 2.0 kg N₂O ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. This was then the number used to transform the response ratios determined in our study to Mg CO₂-eq ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹.

In the other approach, the mean difference was determined directly from the meta-analysis. Although this approach is not the most recommended way to interpret results of a meta-analysis, the benefit is that it provides an absolute value and for skewed distributions, i.e. many low emissions values and few high one, which can be the representative for N₂O emissions, it will provide a more representative result. Nevertheless, both approaches only provide a rough estimate of the effects and do not take account of regional differences. A regional modelling approach, in which both carbon sequestration and N₂O emissions are determined, would provide a better result, but this was beyond the scope of the current study.

In Table 5, the results for the average SOC sequestration and change in N₂O emissions is provided. These numbers are average values at EU level but will vary amongst regions. The average SOC sequestration varies from 0.1 Mg CO₂ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ for reduced tillage to 1.37 Mg CO₂ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ for biochar (over a period of 50 years). For biochar and agroforestry, the N₂O emissions are reduced and will strengthen the mitigation effect of these practices. For the other practices on average, an increase is foreseen, but the increase is (much) lower compared to the SOC sequestration rate. Only for reduced tillage, there is a risk on offsetting the SOC sequestration, as the SOC sequestration rate is low.

Table 5 Comparison of average SOC sequestration rate with change in N₂O emissions

SOC measures	SOC sequestration	Change in N ₂ O emissions		Offset effect*
		Response Ratio approach	Mean difference approach	
	Mg CO ₂ eq ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹	Mg CO ₂ -eq ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹	Mg CO ₂ -eq ha ⁻¹ ya ⁻¹	
Reduced tillage	0.10	0.04	0.11	43% / 106%
No tillage	0.37	0.09	0.11	23% / 29%
Biochar	1.37	-0.17	-0.19	-13% / -14%
Irrigation	0.21	0.09	0.13	44% / 62%
Cover crops	0.21	0.18	0.06	88% / 30%
Crop residues (straw)	0.75	0.12	0.08	16% / 11%
Agroforestry (cropland)	0.55	-0.29	-0.39	-54% / -72%

* Negative numbers mean there is no offset and the measure is enhancing the mitigation effect

If the practices would be implemented on the full area of implementation as stated in Seidel et al. (2024) (EU27 + UK, Norway, Switzerland and Turkey), SOC sequestration would be 115 Mton CO₂ per year and the additional N₂O emissions due to the implementation of the SOC practices would be 1.0 Mton CO₂-eq. However, this area of implementation is very uncertain, as it does not take economic and other barriers into account. Especially for biochar, the uncertainty is high as it depends on the amount of biomass that would actually be available for biochar. Without biochar, SOC sequestration would be 38 Mton CO₂ per year and the N₂O emissions about 11 Mton CO₂-eq per year. In that case, the N₂O emissions are much higher as the reduction due to biochar is not included. Still the N₂O emissions would only off set about 29% of the SOC sequestration and in case the biochar measure is included, it would only offset 1% of the SOC sequestration.

6 Conclusion

This study assessed the most recent studies of agricultural SOC-sequestration measures on soil N₂O emissions to evaluate possible trade-offs within the GHG-mitigation effect. Based on available literature, practices with a trade-off risk (i.e., increasing N₂O emissions while increasing SOC) were cover crops and the incorporation of green crop residues, whereas the practices with a confident synergy are biochar, land-use change towards less N intense systems (grassland or energy crops) and agroforestry.

Organic amendments, mature crop residues, irrigation and reduced tillage showed tendencies to increase the N₂O emissions but not significantly different from zero. We observed a lack of research data specifically on solid livestock manure, land use changes and irrigation due to the relatively low number of observations, especially in European pedoclimatic conditions. There is also a lack of N₂O studies that tackle irrigation specifically in Mediterranean areas, where the use of irrigation alleviates the drought spells that will become more frequent and intense in the future. Although these practices have a limited number of studies, we provided the first quantitative estimates in N₂O emission changes for specific practices.

The overall risk on off-setting the mitigation potential of SOC sequestration by N₂O emissions appears very low. Based on the degree of implementation of SOC sequestration measures in Europe, as determined in CarboSeq, the potential offset varies between 1% and 29%. Although some SOC sequestration measures might increase N₂O emissions, these risks can also be mitigated by appropriate management, for example by using applying organic amendments at the right time or selecting cover crop species with higher CN ratios.

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Annex 1 A literature review of tillage meta-analysis

The effect of tillage practices on N₂O emissions has been widely studied. We found four global meta-analysis and one meta-analysis of Chinese studies alone (Zhao et al. 2016) testing the effect of non-tillage versus conventional tillage. These studies were analysed in more depth and the results are provided in this Annex. In this overview we focus on the results from the global meta-analyses. Two these studies also studied the pooled effect of RT and NT compared to CT (van Kessel et al. 2013, Mei et al. 2018). These meta-analysis combined the effects of 239 (van Kessel et al. 2013), 299 (Huang et al. 2018), 212 (Mei et al. 2018) and 181 (Shakoor et al. 2021) studies.

Due to sufficient global meta-analyses on tillage effects on N₂O we summarized global effects of tillage from these meta-analyses. Three of the global meta-analyses showed an average increase on N₂O emissions under NT that varied from 10.4% to 19.2% (Table A1 *Overall summary effects of existing meta-analyses No-Tillage (NT) /Reduced Tillage (RT) vs. Conventional Tillage (CT)*) (Huang et al. 2018, Mei et al. 2018, Shakoor et al. 2021), whereas the meta-analysis from van Kessel et al. (2013) did not show a significant increase on N₂O emissions.

Table A1 Overall summary effects of existing meta-analyses No-Tillage (NT) /Reduced Tillage (RT) vs. Conventional Tillage (CT)

	van Kessel (2013)	Mei (2018)	Huang (2018)	Shakoor (2021)
Control	CT	CT	CT	CT
Response variables	RT & NT	RT & NT	NT	NT
Scale	Global	Global	Global	Global
Overall Test				
NT vs CT	n.s.	19%	10%	12%
RT vs CT	n.s.	n.s.		
(RT & NT) vs CT	n.s.	18%		

When the meta-analyses tested the effect of RT on N₂O emissions, the effect was not significant (van Kessel et al. 2013, Mei et al. 2018). Absence of a significant effect as well as the large variation within the observations may be explained by the opposing chemical and physical factors that control N₂O emissions related to the nitrification and denitrification process, as well as the oxygen status of the soil that controls the pathway of N₂O production (van Kessel et al. 2013). The heterotrophic denitrification process occurs under anaerobic conditions, whereas nitrification is an aerobic process. Soil physical, biological and chemical factors function together to affect soil N₂O emission dynamics (Mei et al. 2018). Further, agricultural management such as fertili, irrigation and cropping systems imply an important role in N₂O emissions. To better understand the varying effect of tillage on N₂O emissions it is important to test relationship with other explanatory parameters such as: climate, soil properties and management.

Precipitation and temperature are key factors regulating N₂O emissions. Higher rainfall leads to an increased soil moisture content, increasing soil anaerobicity and thus stimulating denitrification and N₂O emissions (Li et al. 2022). Similarly, warm temperature stimulates SOM decomposition and N

turnover, which can increase heterotrophic microbial activity and enhance N₂O emissions (Butterbach-Bahl and Dannenmann 2011). Indeed, Mei et al. (2018) found that N₂O emissions were significantly higher under reduced/no-tillage in tropical and warm temperature climate (N₂O emissions were significantly related to soil texture, with higher emissions from fine textured soils in two meta-analyses (Huang et al. 2018, Mei et al. 2018). Surprisingly the meta-analysis by Shakoor et al. (2021) showed the opposite results. Generally speaking no-tillage decreases the soil bulk density and water holding capacity, which is prone to generate anaerobic microsites, especially in fine-texture soils (Bouwman et al. 2002, Mei et al. 2018, Rochette et al. 2018). Whereas, the results from Shakoor et al. (2021) may be explained with interactive effect related with the oxygen stress produced by the SOM decomposition process in coarse soil that may enhance N₂O emissions.

From the four meta-analysis only Mei et al. (2018) studied the effect of SOC on N₂O emissions. Although their study did not find a significant correlation between SOC and the effect size of NT&RT, they found some apparent characteristic trends in the mean effect size within categories. In general when increased SOC relate with the increased of N₂O emissions under conservation tillage (RT, NT). A similar trend was reported by Li et al. (2005). High SOC provides more substrate for heterotrophic denitrifiers, which should favour enhanced denitrification and N₂O emissions.

Table). Surprisingly Shakoor et al. (2021) found the largest increase in N₂O emissions under cool temperate climates (30%). However, the meta-analysis by Shakoor et al. (2021) does not clearly categorise the differences between the climate zones used, and it references a paper in which the climate zone description is different. Moreover, the correlation between temperature and rainfall is likely clearer than climate zones since local differences may exist in rainfall and temperature within climate zones. van Kessel et al. (2013) showed that in dry climates N₂O emissions were more sensitive to non-tillage or reduced tillage increasing N₂O emissions in the short term, and decreasing in the long term. This trend was not noticed in humid climates, probably because the increase of soil moisture is not enough to vary the amount of N₂O produced in the denitrification process.

The effect of pH on N₂O emissions are not completely straightforward. Generally a high pH increases denitrification, and thus N₂O emissions (Wang et al. 2018b). Yet, the reduction of N₂O to N₂ is also stimulated, thus reducing N₂O emissions (Wang et al. 2018b, Henault et al. 2019, Li et al. 2022). Nitrifiers generally perform well in slightly acidic to slightly alkaline pH (Mørkved et al. 2007). Nitrification was previously assumed not possible at low pH (<5.5) because of the very small amount of ammonia in the soil, however subsequent studies have shown that nitrification is possible to a pH as low as 3 when ammonia-oxidizing archaea instead of bacteria dominate nitrification rates (Li et al. 2018).

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N₂O emissions were significantly related to soil texture, with higher emissions from fine textured soils in two meta-analyses (Huang et al. 2018, Mei et al. 2018). Surprisingly the meta-analysis by Shakoor et al. (2021) showed the opposite results. Generally speaking no-tillage decreases the soil bulk density and water holding capacity, which is prone to generate anaerobic microsites, especially in fine-texture soils (Bouwman et al. 2002, Mei et al. 2018, Rochette et al. 2018). Whereas, the results from Shakoor et al. (2021) may be explained with interactive effect related with the oxygen stress produced by the SOM decomposition process in coarse soil that may enhance N₂O emissions.

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Table A2 Climate, soil properties and agricultural management effects on N₂O as derived from existing meta-analyses Non-Tillage (NT) /Reduced Tillage (RT) vs. Conventional Tillage (CT). Level of significance is indicated by * (p<0.05) or ** (p<0.01)

	van Kessel (2013)	Mei (2018)	Huang (2018)	Shakoor (2021)
Climate	Arid/humid (n.s.)	Tropical (74.1%)	Humid (12.3%)	Warm temperate (19%)
	n.a.	Warm (17%)	Dry (n.s.)	Subtropical (n.s.)
	n.a.	Cold (n.s.)	n.a.	Temperate (n.s.)
	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	Cool temperate (30%)
pH	n.a.	Acidic (21.3%)	Acidic (15%)	Acidic (30%)
		Neutral (n.s.)	n.a.	Neutral (-9.6%)
		Alkaline (13.0%)	n.a.	Alkaline (-12%)
Soil texture	n.a.	Fine/coarse texture (n.s.)	Fine texture (32.2 %)	Fine texture (-24%)
		medium texture (14.3%)	n.a.	Coarse and medium (11.9%)
		clay <20% (42.9%)	n.a.	n.a.
SOC content	n.a.	15-30 SOC g/kg (12%)	n.a.	n.a.
Irrigation	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	Rainfed (14.7%)
Crop residues	n.a.	n.a.	Removed (n.s.)	n.a.
			Retained (n.s.)	
Tillage duration	<10 years (+38%) *	< 3 years (29.3 %)	< 5 years (n.s.)	n.a.
	>10 years (-34%) *	3-10 years (17.3%)	5-10 years (n.s.)	

	n.a.	> 10 years (n.s.)	> 10 years (n.s.)	n.a.
Fertilization placement	<5 cm n.s.	n.a.	Surface (18.6%)	n.a.
	>5cm (27%)**	n.a.	Subsurface (ns)	n.a.

Management practices such as fertilisation or residue incorporation naturally have a direct effect on N₂O emissions by increasing the N content of the soil (Webb et al. 2010, Charles et al. 2017, Abalos et al. 2022b). Besides from a direct effect, residue incorporation or fertilisation with organic fertilisers could also alter the soil moisture status or the microbial community of the soil and thus affect N₂O emissions in an indirect way (Abalos et al. 2022a).

Annex 2 Funnel plots

Figure A.1. Tillage practices funnel plots to check for publication bias.

Figure A.2. Agroforestry funnel plot

Figure A.3. Land Use Change funnel plots

Figure A.4. Irrigation funnel plots

Figure A.5. Crop residue incorporation funnel plots.

Figure A.6. Organic amendments funnel plots.

Figure A.7. Biochar funnel plots.

Annex 3 Forest plots for response ratio

Figure A.8. Agroforestry forest plot for response ratio. Each data point represents a data point from a study. N shows the number of replicates per data point and the diamond indicates the average effect size of the meta-analysis.

Figure A.9. Land Use Change forest plot for response ratio. Each datapoint represents a datapoint from a study. N shows the number of replicates per datapoint and the diamond indicates the average effect size of the meta-analysis.

Figure A.10. Irrigation forest plot for response ratio. Each datapoint represents a datapoint from a study. N shows the number of replicates per datapoint and the diamond indicates the average effect size of the meta-analysis.

Figure A.11. The effects of no tillage and reduced tillage practices on N₂O emissions compared to conventional tillage. Each datapoint represents a datapoint from a study. N shows the number of replicates per datapoint and the diamond indicates the average effect size of the meta-analysis.

Figure A.12. Forest plot for response ratio of crop residue incorporation on N₂O emissions compared to crop residue removal. Each datapoint represents a datapoint from a study. N shows the number of replicates per datapoint and the diamond indicates the average effect size of the meta-analysis.

Figure A.14. Forest plot for response ratio of biochar practices on N₂O emissions compared to no addition of biochar. Each datapoint represents a datapoint from a study. N shows the number of replicates per datapoint and the diamond indicates the average effect size of the meta-analysis.

Annex 4 Forest plots for raw mean difference

Figure A.15. Agroforestry forest plot for raw mean difference. Each datapoint represents a datapoint from a study. N shows the number of replicates per datapoint and the diamond indicates the average raw mean difference of the meta-analysis.

Figure A.16. Irrigation forest plot for raw mean difference. Each datapoint represents a datapoint from a study. *N* shows the number of replicates per datapoint and the diamond indicates the average raw mean difference of the meta-analysis.

Figure A.17. No tillage and reduced tillage forest plot for raw mean difference. Each datapoint represents a datapoint from a study. N shows the number of replicates per datapoint and the diamond indicates the average raw mean difference of the meta-analysis.

Publication **n** **Estimate [95% CI]**

Figure A.18. Crop residue forest plot for raw mean difference. Each datapoint represents a datapoint from a study. N shows the number of replicates per datapoint and the diamond indicates the average raw mean difference of the meta-analysis.

Figure A.19. Organic amendment forest plot for raw mean difference. Each datapoint represents a datapoint from a study. N shows the number of replicates per datapoint and the diamond indicates the average raw mean difference of the meta-analysis.

Figure A.20. Biochar forest plot for raw mean difference. Each datapoint represents a datapoint from a study. N shows the number of replicates per datapoint and the diamond indicates the average raw mean difference of the meta-analysis.